

Applications of Geometric Algorithms to Reduce Interference in Wireless Mesh Network

Hung-Chin Jang

Department of Computer Science, National Chengchi University, Taiwan

ABSTRACT

In wireless mesh networks such as WLAN (IEEE 802.11s) or WMAN (IEEE 802.11), each node should help to relay packets of neighboring nodes toward gateway using multi-hop routing mechanisms. Wireless mesh networks usually intensively deploy mesh nodes to deal with the problem of dead spot communication. However, the higher density of nodes deployed, the higher radio interference occurred. This causes significant degradation of system performance. In this paper, we first convert network problems into geometry problems in graph theory, and then solve the interference problem by geometric algorithms. We first define line intersection in a graph to reflect radio interference problem in a wireless mesh network. We then use plan sweep algorithm to find intersection lines, if any; employ Voronoi diagram algorithm to delimit the regions among nodes; use Delaunay Triangulation algorithm to reconstruct the graph in order to minimize the interference among nodes. Finally, we use standard deviation to prune off those longer links (higher interference links) to have a further enhancement. The proposed hybrid solution is proved to be able to significantly reduce interference in a wireless mesh network in $O(n \log n)$ time complexity.

KEYWORDS

Wireless Mesh Network, Interference Reduction, Voronoi Diagram, Delaunay Triangulation Algorithm

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/0310jgraph6.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2010.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Alicherry, R. Bhatia and E. Li, (2005) "[Joint Channel Assignment and Routing for Throughput Optimization in Multi-Radio Wireless Mesh Networks](#)" Proceedings of ACM MOBICOM, pp. 58-72.
- [2] M . de Berg , O. Cheong, M . van Kreveld and M . Overmars , (2008) "[Computational Geometry :Algorithms and Applications,](#)" Third Edition .

- [3] M. Burkhart , P . von Rickenbach , R . Wattenhofer and A . Zollinger , (2004) “[Does Topology Control Reduce Interference ?](#)” Proceedings of the 5th ACM Int . Symposium on Mobile Ad-hoc Networking and Computing (MobiHoc), pp . 9-19 .
- [4] P. Gupta and P.R. Kumar, (2000) “[The Capacity of Wireless Network](#)” IEEE Transactions on Information Theory, Vol. 46, No. 2 , pp. 388-404.
- [5] P . H . Hsiao and H . T . Kung, (2005) “[Constructing Multiple Wireless Meshes in the Same Region with Beam-Crossing Grids,](#)” Proceedings of IEEE WCNC .
- [6] L. Hu, (1993) “[Topology Control for Multihop Packet Radio Networks,](#)” IEEE Transactions on Communication, Vol. 41 , No. 10 , pp. 1474 -1481 .
- [7] K . Jain , J . Padhye , V . N . Padmanabhan and L . Qiu , (2005) “[Impact of Interference on Multi-Hop Wireless Network Performance](#)” , Springer Science + Business Media , Inc .
Manufactured in The Netherlands , pp. 471-487 .
- [8] M. Kodialam and T. Nandagopal, (2003) “[Characterizing Achievable Rates in Multi-Hop Wireless Networks: the Joint Routing and Scheduling Problem,](#)” Proceedings of ACM MOBICOM, pp. 42-54.
- [9] V. S. A. Kumar, M. V. Marathe, S. Parthasarathy and A. Srinivasan, (2005) “[Algorithmic Aspects of Capacity in Wireless Networks,](#)” Proceedings of ACM SIGMETRICS, pp. 133-144.
- [10] P. Kyasanur and N. H. Vaidya, (2005) “[Routing and Interface Assignment in Multi-Channel MultiInterface Wireless Networks,](#)” Proceedings of IEEE WCNC.
- [11] S. Meguerdichian , F. Koushanfar, M. Potkonjak and M . B . Srivastava, (2001) “Coverage Problems in Wireless Ad-Hoc Sensor Networks,” Proceedings of IEEE INFOCOM, pp. 1380-1387.
- [12] K. Moaveninejad and X. Y. Li, (2005) “[Low-Interference Topology Control for Wireless Ad Hoc Networks,](#)” Journal of Ad Hoc and Sensor Wireless Networks.
- [13] J. Padhye, S. Agarwal, V. Padmanaban, L. Qiu, A. Rao and B. Zill, (2005) “[Estimation of Link Interference in Static Multi-Hop Wireless Networks,](#)” Proceedings of IMC.
- [14] K. Ramachandran, E. Belding, K. Almeroth and M. Buddhikot, (2006) “[Interference-Aware Channel Assignment in Multi-Radio Wireless Mesh Networks,](#)” Proceedings of IEEE INFOCOM.
- [15] R. Ramanathan and R. Rosales-Hain, (2000) “Topology Control of Multihop Wireless Networks Using Transmit Power Adjustment,” Proceedings of IEEE INFOCOM.
- [16] C. Reis, R. Mahajan, M. Rodrig, D. Wetherall and J. Zahorjan, (2006) “[Measurement-Based Models of Delivery and Interference in Static Wireless Networks,](#)” Proceedings of ACM SIGCOMM.

[17] V. Rodoplu and T. H. Meng, (1999) "[Minimum Energy Mobile Wireless Networks](#)," IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, Vol. 17.

[18] A. P. Subramanian, H. Gupta and S. R. Das, (2008) "[Minimum Interference Channel Assignment in Multiradio Wireless Mesh Networks](#)," IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, Vol. 7, No. 11 , pp. 1459-1473.

[19] J. Tang, G. Xue and W. Zhang, (2005) "[Interference-Aware Topology Control and QoS Routing in Multi-Channel Wireless Mesh Networks](#)," International Symposium on Mobile Ad Hoc Networking & Computing, pp. 68-77.

Citation count 61

Survey and Taxonomy of Unicast Routing Protocols for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks

Natarajan Meghanathan¹

¹Jackson State University, 1400 Lynch St, Jackson, MS, USA

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to survey the unicast routing protocols for mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) and study their primary route selection principle. In this context, we did an exhaustive survey of unicast MANET routing protocols proposed in the literature. Qualitatively, based on their primary route selection principle, we show that all these protocols could be placed under one of two broad route selection categories: routing based on minimum-weight path and routing based on stability. In addition to the primary route selection principle, we also identify the underlying routing metric and the routing philosophy (proactive, reactive, flat, hierarchical, location-awareness, power-sensitiveness and multipath capability) adopted by the different routing protocols. We believe the survey can be a great source of information for researchers in ad hoc networks.

KEYWORDS

Routing Protocols, Survey, Mobile Ad hoc Networks, Unicast, Stability, Minimum-Weight Path

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/1209s1.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/Currentissue.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Agarwal, A. Ahuja, J. P. Singh and R. Shorey, "[Route-Life Time Assessment Based Routing Protocol for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks](#)," Proceedings of IEEE ICC, June 2000.
- [2] G. Aggelou and R. Tafazolli, "RDMAR: A Bandwidth Efficient Routing Protocol for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks," Proceedings of the 2nd ACM international workshop on Wireless mobile multimedia, pp. 26 – 33, August 1999.
- [3] S. Basagni, I. Chlamtac, V. R. Syrotiuk, B. A. Woodward, "A Distance Routing Effect Algorithm for Mobility (DREAM)," Proceedings of MobiCom, pp. 76 – 84, October 1998.
- [4] B. Bellur, R. G. Ogier, "[A Reliable Efficient Topology Broadcast Protocol for Dynamic Networks](#)," Proceedings of IEEE INFOCOM, pp. 178 – 186, 1999.
- [5] L. Blazevic, L. Buttyan, S. Capkun, S. Giordano, J-P. Hubaux and J-Y. Boudec, "[Self-Organization in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks: The Approach of Terminodes](#)," IEEE Communications Magazine, pp. 166– 174, June 2001.
- [6] J.-H. Chang and L. Tassiulas, "[Energy Conserving Routing in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks](#)," Proceedings of IEEE INFOCOM, pp. 22 – 31, March 2000.
- [7] T-W Chen and M. Gerla, "Global State Routing: A New Routing Scheme for Ad-hoc Wireless Networks," Proceedings of IEEE ICC, pp. 171 – 175, June 1998.
- [8] C.-C. Chiang, "[Routing in Clustered, Multi-hop, Mobile Wireless Networks with Fading Channel](#)," Proceedings IEEE SICON, pp. 197 – 211, April 1997.
- [9] C.-F. Chiasserini and R. R. Rao, "[Routing Protocols to Maximize Battery Efficiency](#)," Proceedings of IEEE MILCOM, pp. 496 – 500, Vol. 1, October 2000.
- [10] T. Clausen, P. Jacquet, A. Laouiti, P. Muhlethaler, A. Qayyum and L. Viennot, "[Optimized Link State Routing Protocol for Ad Hoc Networks](#)," Proceedings of IEEE INMIC, pp. 62 – 68, December 2001.
- [11] M. S. Corson and A. Ephremides, "A Distributed Algorithm for Mobile Wireless Networks," Wireless Networks, Vol. 1, pp. 61 – 81, 1995.
- [12] M. S. Corson and V. D. Park, "Link Reversal Routing," Ad Hoc Networking, edited by Charles E. Perkins, Chapter 8, pp. 255 – 298, Addison Wesley, 2001.
- [13] V. Devarapalli, A. A. Selcuk and D. Sindhu, "Multicast Zone Routing (MZR) Protocol," Internet Draft, draft-vijay-manet- mzs-01.txt, work in progress, June 2001.
- [14] R. Dube, C. D. Rais, K-Y. Wang and S. K. Tripathi, "[Signal Stability based Adaptive Routing for Ad Hoc Wireless Networks](#)," IEEE Personal Communications, pp. 36 – 45, February 1997.
- [15] J. Eriksson, M. Faloutsos, S. Krishnamurthy, "Scalable Ad Hoc Routing: The Case for Dynamic Addressing," Proceedings of IEEE INFOCOM, 2004.

- [16] L. R. Ford Jr. and D. R. Fulkerson, Flows in Networks, Princeton University Press, 1962.
- [17] E. Gafni and D. Bertsekas, "[Distributed Algorithms for Generating Loop-free Routes in Networks with Frequently Changing Topology](#)," IEEE Transactions on Communication, Vol. 29, No. 1, pp. 11 – 15, Jan. 1981.
- [18] J. J. Garcia-Luna and M. Spohn, "[Source Tree Adaptive Routing](#)," draft- ietf-manet-star-00.txt, work in progress, October 1999.
- [19] J. Gomez, A. Campbell, M. Naghshineh, C. Bisdikian, "PARO: Supporting Dynamic Power Controlled Routing in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks," Wireless Networks, Vol. 9, No. 5, pp. 443-460, Sep 2003.
- [20] S. Guha and S. Khuller, "[Approximation Algorithms for Connected Dominating Sets](#)," Technical Report 3660, University of Maryland, June 1996.
- [21] M. Gunes, U. Sorges and I. Bouazizi, "ARA: The Ant Colony based Routing Algorithm for MANETS," Proceedings of the 2002 ICPP Workshop on Ad Hoc Networks (IWAHN 2002), pp. 79- 85, August 2002
- [22] S. Guo and O. W. Yang, "Performance of Backup Source Routing in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks," Proceedings of IEEE WCNC, pp. 440-444, 2002.
- [23] Z. J. Haas, M. R. Pearlman and P. Samar, "The Bordercast Resolution Protocol (BRP) for Ad Hoc Networks," draft- ietf-manet-zone-brp-02.txt, work in progress, July 2002.
- [24] Z. J. Haas, M. R. Pearlman and P. Samar, "The Interzone Routing Protocol (IERP) for Ad Hoc Networks," draft- ietf-manet-zone-ierp-02.txt, work in progress, July 2002.

Citation count 59

A COMPARISON OF LINK LAYER ATTACKS ON WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

Dr. Shahriar Mohammadi¹ and Hossein Jadidoleslami²

**1 Information Technology Engineering Group, Department of Industrial
Engineering,**

K.N. Tossi University of Technology, Tehran, Iran

**2 Master of Science Student, Department of Information Technology, University
of
Guilan, Guilan, Iran**

ABSTRACT

Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) have many potential applications [1, 5] and unique challenges. They usually consist of hundreds or thousands small sensor nodes such as MICA2, which operate autonomously; conditions such as cost, invisible deployment and many application domains, lead to small size and limited resources sensors [2]. WSNs are susceptible to many types of link layer attacks [1] and most of traditional networks security techniques are unusable on WSNs [2]; due to wireless and shared nature of communication channel, untrusted transmissions, deployment in open environments, unattended nature and limited resources [1]. So, security is a vital requirement for these networks; but we have to design a proper security mechanism that attends to WSN's constraints and requirements. In this paper, we focus on security of WSNs, divide it (the WSNs security) into four categories and will consider them, include: an overview of WSNs, security in WSNs, the threat model on WSNs, a wide variety of WSNs' link layer attacks and a comparison of them. This work enables us to identify the purpose and capabilities of the attackers; also, the goal and effects of the link layer attacks on WSNs are introduced. Also, this paper discusses known approaches of security detection and defensive mechanisms against the link layer attacks; this would enable it security managers to manage the link layer attacks of WSNs more effectively.

KEYWORDS

Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), Security, Link Layer, Attacks, Detection, Defensive Mechanism

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/3111jgraph03.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2011.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Znaidi, M. Minier and J. P. Babau; An Ontology for Attacks in Wireless Sensor Networks; INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET EN AUTOMATIQUE (INRIA); Oct 2008.
- [2] K. Sharma and M. K. Ghose; Wireless Sensor Networks: An Overview on its Security Threats; IJCA, Special Issue on "Mobile Ad-hoc Networks" MANETs; CSE Department, SMIT, Sikkim, India; 2010.
- [3] K. Xing, S. Sundhar, R. Srinivasan, M. Rivera, J. Li and X. Cheng; Attacks and Countermeasures in Sensor Networks: A Survey; Computer Science Department, George Washington University; Springer, Network Security; 2005.
- [4] T. A. Zia; A Security Framework for Wireless Sensor Networks; Doctor of Philosophy Thesis; The School of Information Technologies, University of Sydney; Feb 2008.
- [5] M. Saxena; Security in Wireless Sensor Networks: A Layer-based Classification; Department of Computer Science, Purdue University.

- [6] Z. Li and G. Gong; A Survey on Security in Wireless Sensor Networks; Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Waterloo, Canada.
- [7] A. Dimitrievski, V. Pejovska and D. Davcev; Security Issues and Approaches in WSN; Department of computer science, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology; Skopje, Republic of Macedonia.
- [8] J. Yick, B. Mukherjee and D. Ghosal; Wireless Sensor Network Survey; Elsevier's Computer Networks Journal 52 (2292-2330); Department of Computer Science, University of California; 2008.
- [9] G. padmavathi and D. Shanmugapriya; A Survey of Attacks, Security Mechanisms and Challenges in Wireless Sensor Networks; International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS),vol. 4, No. 1& 2; Department of Computer Science, Avinashilingam University for Women, Coimbatore, India; 2009.
- [10] C. Karlof and D. Wagner; Secure Routing in Wireless Sensor Networks: Attacks and Countermeasures; Elsevier's AdHoc Networks Journal, Special Issue on Sensor Network Applications and Protocols; In First IEEE International Workshop on Sensor Network Protocols and Applications; University of California at Berkeley, Berkeley, USA; 2003.
- [11] A. Perrig, R. Szewczyk, V. Wen, D. culler and D. Tygar; SPINS: Security Protocols for Sensor Networks; Wireless Networking ACM CCS; 2003.
- [12] I. Krontiris, T. Giannetsos and T. Dimitriou; Launching a Sinkhole Attack in Wireless Sensor Networks, the Intruder Side; Athens Information Technology, Peania; Athens, Greece.
- [13] A. Perrig, J. Stankovic and D. Wagner; Security in Wireless Sensor Networks; In Communications of the ACM Vol. 47, No. 6, 2004.
- [14] A. Saini and H. Kumar; Comparison Between Various Black Hole Detection Techniques in MANET; Panjab University, Chandigarh; National Conference on Computational Instrumentation (NCCI); Mar 2010.
- [15] R. Maheshwari, J. Gao and S. R. Das; Detecting Wormhole Attacks in Wireless Networks Using Connectivity Information; IEEE INFOCOM; Alaska; 2007.
- [16] Y. Hu, A. Perrig and D. B. Johnson; Rushing Attacks and Defense in Wireless Ad Hoc Network Routing Protocols; ACM; Carnegie Mellon University; Rice University; San Diego, California, USA; Sep 2003.
- [17] I. Ullah and S. U. Rehman; Analysis of Black Hole attack On MANETs Using Different MANET Routing Protocols; Master Thesis, Electrical Engineering, Thesis no: MEE-2010-2698; School of Computing Blekinge Institute of Technology, Sweden; Jun 2010.
- [18] C. Tumrongwittayapak and R. Varakulsiripunth; Detecting Sinkhole Attacks in Wireless Sensor Networks; ICROS-SICE International Conference; 2009.

- [19] Y. Zhou, Y. Fang and Y. Zhang; Security Wireless Sensor Networks: A Survey; IEEE Communication Surveys; 2008.
- [20] Y. Wang, G. Attebury and B. Ramamurthy; A Survey of Security Issues in Wireless Sensor Networks; IEEE Communication Surveys; 2006.
- [21] R. H. Khokhar, M. A. Ngadi and S. Mandala; A Review of Current Routing Attacks in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks; Faculty of Computer Science and Information System, Department of Computer System & Communication, University Technology Malaysia (UTM); Malaysia.
- [22] T. Kavitha and D. Sridharan; Security Vulnerabilities in Wireless Sensor Networks: A Survey; Journal of Information Assurance and Security; 2009.
- [23] B. Parno and A. Perrig; Distributed Detection of Node Replication Attacks in Sensor Networks; Carnegie Mellon University.
- [24] J. R. Douceur; the Sybil Attack; Proc. 1st ACM Int'l. Wksp. Peer-to-Peer Systems; 2002.
- [25] J. Newsome, E. Shi, D. Song and A. Perrig; the Sybil Attack in Sensor Networks: Analysis & Defenses; Center for Computer and Communications Security; 2004.
- [26] L. Hu and D. Evans; Using Directional Antennas to Prevent Wormhole Attacks; In Network and Distributed System Security Symposium (NDSS); 2004.
- [27] Y. Hu, A. Perrig and D. Johnson; Packet Leashes: A Defense against Wormhole Attacks in Wireless Networks; Proc. 22nd Annual Joint Conference of the IEEE Computer and Communications Societies; 2003.
- [28] A. Wood and J. Stankovic; Denial of Service in Sensor Networks; IEEE Computer Mag.; 2002.

Citation count 29

AN EFFICIENT METHOD BASED ON GENETIC ALGORITHMS TO SOLVE SENSOR NETWORK OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

Ehsan Heidari¹ and Ali Movaghar²

¹Department of Computer Engineering, Islamic Azad University, Doroud, Iran

²Department of Computer Engineering, Sharif University of Technology, Tehran, Iran

ABSTRACT

Minimization of the number of cluster heads in a wireless sensor network is a very important problem to reduce channel contention and to improve the efficiency of the algorithm when executed at the level of cluster-heads. In this paper, we propose an efficient method based on genetic algorithms (GAs) to solve a sensor network optimization problem. Long communication distances between sensors and a sink in a sensor network can greatly drain the energy of sensors and reduce the lifetime of a network. By clustering a sensor network into a number of independent clusters using a GA, we can greatly minimize the total communication distance, thus prolonging the network lifetime. Simulation results show that our algorithm can quickly find a good solution.

KEYWORDS

Wireless Sensor Networks, Longevity of Network, Communication Distance, Clustering, Genetic Algorithm

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/3111jgraph02.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2011.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Akyildiz I. F., W. Su, Y. Sankarasubramaniam, E. Cayirci., “Wireless sensor networks: a survey”, Journal of Computer Networks, Vol. 38, March 2002, pp. 393-422.
- [2] Al-Karaki J. N. and A. E. Kamal, “Routing Techniques in Wireless Sensor Networks: A Survey”, IEEE Journal of Wireless Communications, vol. 11, no. 6, Dec. 2004, pp. 6–28.
- [3] Amini N., M. Fazeli, S. G. Miremadi and M. T. Manzuri, “Distance-Based Segmentation: An Energy-Efficient Clustering Hierarchy for Wireless Microsensor Networks”, Proc. of the 5th Annual Conf. on Communication Networks and Services Research (CNSR 2007), Fredericton, Canada, May 2007, pp. 18-25.
- [4] Calhoun B. H., D.C. Daly, N. Verma, D.F. Finchelstein, D.D. Wentzloff, A. Wang, S. Cho and A.P. Chandrakasan, “Design Considerations for Ultra-Low Energy Wireless Microsensor Nodes”, IEEE Trans. on Computers, vol. 54, no. 6, Jun. 2005, pp. 727-740.
- [5] D. Turgut, S. K. Das, R. Elmasri, and B. Turgut, “Optimizing clustering algorithm in mobile ad hoc networks using genetic algorithmic approach,” in Proceedings of the Global Telecommunications Conference (GLOBECOM), November 2002.
- [6] Dr Alex Rogers , CM2408 – Symbolic AI Lecture 8 – Introduction to Genetic Algorithms ,December 2002.

- [7] Heinzelman W. R., A. P. Chandrakasan and H. Balakrishnan, "An Application-Specific Protocol Architecture for Wireless Microsensor Networks", IEEE Trans. on Wireless Communications, vol. 1, no. 4, Oct. 2002, pp. 660-670.
- [8] Heinzelman W. R., A. P. Chandrakasan and H. Balakrishnan, "Energy-Efficient Communication Protocol for Wireless Microsensor Networks", Proc. of the 33rd IEEE Int. Conf. on System Sciences, Honolulu, USA, Jan. 2000, pp. 1-10.
- [9] J. Tillett, R. Rao, F. Sahin, and T.M. Rao. Cluster-head Identification in Ad hoc Sensor Networks Using Particle Swarm Optimization. In Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Personal Wireless Communication, 2002.
- [10] Katz R. H., J. M. Kahn and K. S. J. Pister, "Mobile Networking for Smart Dust", Proc. of the 5th Annual ACM/IEEE Int. Conf. on Mobile Computing and Networking (MobiCom'99), Seattle, USA, Aug. 1999, pp. 350-355.
- [11] Khadivi A. and M. Shiva, "FTPASC: A Fault Tolerant Power Aware Protocol with Static Clustering for Wireless Sensor Networks", Proc. of IEEE Int. Conf. on Wireless and Mobile Computing, Networking and Communications, Montreal, Canada, Jun. 2006, pp. 397-401.
- [12] Khadivi A., M. Shiva and N. Yazdani, "EPMPAC: an efficient power management protocol with adaptive clustering for wireless sensor networks", Proc. of Int. Conf. on Wireless Communications, Networking and Mobile Computing, China, Sept. 2005, pp. 1154-1157.
- [13] Manjeshwar A. and D. P. Agarwal, "APTEEN: A Hybrid Protocol for Efficient Routing and Comprehensive Information Retrieval in Wireless Sensor Networks," Proc. of the IEEE IPDPS, Fort Lauderdale, USA, Apr. 2002, pp. 195-202.
- [14] Manjeshwar A. and D. P. Agarwal, "TEEN: A Routing Protocol for Enhanced Efficiency in Wireless Sensor Networks", Proc. of the IEEE IPDPS, San Francisco, USA, Apr. 2001, pp 23-26.
- [15] Mehrdad Dianati , Insop Song , Mark Treiber , An Introduction to Genetic Algorithms and Evolution Strategies , University of Waterloo , Canada , 2002.
- [16] Min R., M. Bhardwaj, S. Cho, E. Shih, A. Sinha, A. Wang, and A. Chandrakasan, "Low Power Wireless Sensor Networks", Proc. of International Conf. on VLSI Design, Bangalore, India, Jan. 2001, pp. 205-210.
- [17] Ossama Younis, Marwan Krunz, and Srinivasan Ramasubramanian, "Node Clustering in Wireless Sensor Networks: Recent Developments and Deployment Challenges," IEEE Network (special issue on wireless sensor networking), vol. 20, issue 3, pp. 20-25, May 2006
- [18] S. Bandyopadhyay and E. J. Coyle, "An energy efficient hierarchical clustering algorithm for wireless sensor networks." in Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Communications (INFOCOM), 2003.
- [19] S. Lindsey and C. S. Raghavendra, "PEGASIS: Power-efficient gathering in sensor information systems," in Proceedings of the IEEE Aerospace Conference, March 2002.

[20] Subramanian L. and R. H. Katz, “An Architecture for Building Self Configurable Systems”, Proc. of IEEE/ACM Workshop on Mobile Ad Hoc Networking and Computing, Boston, USA, Aug. 2000, pp. 63-73.

[21] Tanenbaum A. S., C. Gamage and B. Crispo, “Taking Sensor Networks from the Lab to the Jungle”, IEEE Computer Magazine, vol. 39, no. 8, Aug. 2006, pp. 98-100.

[22] W. Ye, J. Heidemann, and D. Estrin, “Medium access control with coordinated adaptive sleeping for wireless sensor networks,” IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networks, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 493– 506, 2004.

[23] <http://geneticalgorithms.ai-depot.com/Tutorial/Overview.html>

Citation count 23

Case Study On Social Engineering Techniques for Persuasion

Mosin Hasan¹ , Nilesh Prajapati² and Safvan Vohara³
1Computer Department, BVM Engineering College, V V Nagar
2IT Department, BVM Engineering College, V V Nagar
3Computer Department, BVM Engineering College, V V Nagar

ABSTRACT

There are plenty of security software in market; each claiming the best, still we daily face problem of viruses and other malicious activities. If we know the basic working principal of such malware then we can very easily prevent most of them even without security software. Hackers and crackers are experts in psychology to manipulate people into giving them access or the information necessary to get access. This paper discusses the inner working of such attacks. Case study of Spyware is provided. In this case study, we got 100% success using social engineering techniques for deception on Linux operating system, which is considered as the most secure operating system. Few basic principal of defend, for the individual as well as for the organization, are discussed here, which will prevent most of such attack if followed.

KEYWORDS

Spyware, Malware, Social Engineering, Psychology.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/0610jgraph2.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2010.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Malware : Threat to the Economy, Survey Study by Mosin Hasan, National Conference IT and Business Intelligence (ITBI - 08)
- [2] White paper: Avoiding Social Engineering and Phishing Attacks,Cyber Security Tip ST04-014, by Mindi McDowell,Carnegie Mellon University, June 2007.
- [3] Book of 'People Hacking' by Harl
- [4] FCAC Cautions Consumers About New “Vishing” Scam, Financial Consumer Agency of Canada, July 25, 2006.
- [5] Schulman, Jay. Voice-over-IP Scams Set to Grow, VoIP News, July 21, 2006.
- [6] Spying Linux: Consequences, Technique and Prevention by Mosin Hasan, IEEE International Advance Computing Conference (IACC'09)
- [7] Redmon,- audit and policy Social Engineering manipulating source , Author: Jared Kee,SANS institute.
- [8] White paper ‘Management Update: How Businesses Can Defend against Social Engineering Attacks’ published on March 16, 2005 by Gartner.
- [9] White paper, Social Engineering:An attack vector most intricate to tackle by Ashish Thapar.
- [10] The Origin of Social Engineering Bt Heip Dand MacAFEE Security Journal, Fall 2008.
- [11] Psychology: A Precious Security Tool by Yves Lafrance,SANS Institute,2004.
- [12] SOCIAL ENGINEERING: A MEANS TO VIOLATE A COMPUTER SYSTEM, By Malcolm Allen, SANS Institute, 2007
- [13] Inside Spyware – Techniques, Remedies and Cure by Mosin hasan Emerging Trends in Computer Technology National Conference.

Citation count 20

Constructing Minimum Connected Dominating Set: Algorithmic approach

**G.N. Purohit and Usha Sharma Centre for Mathematical Sciences,
Banasthali University, Rajasthan 304022**

Abstract

Connected Dominating Set is popularly used for constructing virtual backbones for broadcasting operation in WSNs. UD Graph is the most suitable model for a wireless sensor network. In this paper we provide an algorithm to find MCDS in UD Graph. It is based on the computation of convex hulls of sensor nodes or vertices. Constructing a virtual backbone in WSNs is an important issue because it reduces unnecessary message transmission or flooding in the network. It helps in reducing interference and energy consumption because a limited number of sensors are engaged in message transmission and thus it helps in improving the Quality of Service (QoS) in the network.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/0910jgraph5.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2010.html>

References

- [1] B. N. Clark, C. J. Colbourn and D. S. Johnson, “Unit disk graphs”, Discrete Math, Vol. 86, pages 165–177, 1990
- [2] G. N. Purohit, S. Verma and U. Sharma, “Powers of a Graph and Associated Graph Labeling”, (IJCNS) International Journal of Computer and Network Security, Vol. 2, No.4, pages 45-49, April 2010
- [3] K. Alzoubi, P.-J. Wan and O. Frieder, “New distributed algorithm for connected dominating set in wireless ad hoc networks” in Proc. IEEE HICSS35, January 2002
- [4] K. Islam, S. G. Akl and H. Meijer, “A Constant Factor Distributed Algorithm for computing Connected Dominating Sets in Wireless sensor Networks”
- [5] M. Rai, S. Verma and S. Tapaswi, “A Power Aware Minimum Connected Dominating Set for Wireless Sensor Networks”, Journal of Networks, Vol. 4, No. 6, pages 511-519, August 2009
- [6] S. Guha and S. Khuller, “Approximation algorithms for connected dominating sets” Algorithmica, pages 374–387, 1998
- [7] Y. Li, S. Zhu, M.Thai and D. Du, “Localized Construction of Connected Dominating Set in Wireless Networks” in Proc. TAWN, June 2004

Citation count 19

Classification and Evaluation of Mobility Metrics for Mobility Model Movement Patterns in Mobile

Santosh Kumar S C Sharma Bhupendra Suman Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee-India

ABSTRACT

A mobile ad hoc network is collection of self configuring and adaption of wireless link between communicating devices (mobile devices) to form an arbitrary topology and multihop wireless connectivity without the use of existing infrastructure. It requires efficient dynamic routing protocol to determine the routes subsequent to a set of rules that enables two or more devices to communicate with each others. This paper basically classifies and evaluates the mobility metrics into two categories- direct mobility metrics and derived mobility metrics. These two mobility metrics has been used to measure different mobility models, this paper considers some of mobility models i.e Random Waypoint Model, Reference Point Group Mobility Model, Random Direction Mobility Model, Random Walk Mobility Model, Probabilistic Random Walk, Gauss Markov, Column Mobility Model, Nomadic Community Mobility Model and Manhattan Grid Model.

KEYWORDS

Mobility metrics, Mobility Models, Connectivity Graph

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/0911jgraph03.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2011.html>

Reference

- [1] G.S. Lauer, Packet-radio routing, in: Routing in Communications Networks, ed. M.E. Steenstrup (Prentice Hall, 1995) chapter 11, pp. 351–396.
- [2] S. Ramanathan and M.E. Steenstrup, A survey of routing techniques for mobile communications networks, Mobile Networks and Applications 1 (1996) 98–104.
- [3] F. Bai, A. Helmy, “A Survey of Mobility Modeling and Analysis in Wireless Adhoc Networks” in Wireless Ad Hoc and Sensor Networks, Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2004.
- [4] Nils Aschenbruck, Elmar Gerhards-Padilla, and Peter Martini, “A survey on mobility models for performance analysis in tactical mobile networks”, JTIT, 2/2008, pp: 54-61.

- [5] N. Aschenbruck, E. Gerhards-Padilla, M. Gerharz, M. Frank, and P. Martini, "Modelling mobility in disaster area scenarios", in Proc.10th ACM IEEE Int. Symp. Model. Anal. Simul. Wirel. Mob. Syst.MSWIM, Chania, Greece, 2007.
- [6] F. Bai, N. Sadagopan, and A. Helmy, "IMPORTANT: a framework to systematically analyze the impact of mobility on performance of routing protocols for adhoc networks", in Proc. IEEE INFOCOM, San Francisco, USA, 2003, pp. 825–835.
- [7] Santosh Kumar, S. C. Sharma, Bhupendra Suman," Mobility Metrics Based Classification & Analysis of Mobility Model for Tactical Network", International journal of next- generation networks (IJNGN) Vol.2, No.3September 2010, pp.39-51.
- [8] C. Bettstetter, G. Resta, and P. Santi, "The node distribution of the random waypoint mobility model for wireless ad hoc networks", IEEE Trans. Mob. Comp., vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 257–269, 2003.
- [9] C. Bettstetter and C. Wagner, "The spatial node distribution of the random waypoint mobility model", in Proc. 1st German Worksh. Mob. Ad-Hoc Netw. WMAN'02, Ulm, Germany, 2002, pp. 41–58.
- [10] V. Davies. Evaluating mobility models within an ad hoc network. Master's thesis, Colorado School of Mines, 2000.
- [11] C. Chiang. Wireless Network Multicasting. PhD thesis, University of California, Los Angeles, 1998.
- [12] E. Royer, P.M. Melliar-Smith, and L. Moser. An analysis of the optimum node density for ad hoc mobile networks. In Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), 2001.
- [13] X. Hong, M. Gerla, G. Pei, and C. Chiang. A group mobility model for ad hoc wireless networks. In Proceedings of the ACM International Workshop on Modeling and Simulation of Wireless and Mobile Systems (MSWiM), August 1999.
- [14] V. Tolety. Load reduction in ad hoc networks using mobile servers. Master's thesis, Colorado School of Mines, 1999.
- [15] M. Sanchez. Mobility models. <http://www.disca.upv.es/misan/mobmodel.htm>. Accessed on May 13, 2001.
- [16] Sanchez and P. Manzoni. A java based simulator for ad-hoc networks. <http://www.scs.org/confernc/wmc99/errata/websim/w408/w408.html>. Accessed on May 13,2001.
- [17] European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI): Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS) - Selection procedures for the choice of radio transmission technologies of the UMTS. UMTS 30.03 version 3.2.0, TR 101 112. 1998.
- [18] P. Johansson, T. Larsson, N. Hedman, B. Mielczarek, and M. Degermark. Scenario-based performance analysis of routing protocols for mobile ad-hoc networks. In International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking (MobiCom'99), pages 195–206, 1999

[19] A. B. McDonald and T. Znati. Link availability models for mobile ad-Hoc networks. Technical Report TR99-07, University of Pittsburgh, Department of Computer Science, May 1999.

[20] “A Mobility Scenario Generation and Analysis Tool”, Version: December 22, 2010, Copyright c 2002-2010 University of Bonn.

[21] B. Liang and Z. Haas. Predictive distance-based mobility management for PCS networks. In Proceedings of the Joint Conference of the IEEE Computer and Communications Societies (INFOCOM), March 1999.

[22] The network simulator - ns-allinone-2.34.

Citation count 19

A REVIEW OF INTERFERENCE REDUCTION IN WIRELESS NETWORKS USING GRAPH COLORING METHODS

Maaly A. Hassan¹ and Andrew Chickadel²

¹Department of Computer Engineering, Islamic University of Gaza, Gaza, Palestine

²Department of Computer Science, Villanova University, Villanova, USA

ABSTRACT

The interference imposes a significant negative impact on the performance of wireless networks. With the continuous deployment of larger and more sophisticated wireless networks, reducing interference in such networks is quickly being focused upon as a problem in today's world. In this paper we analyze the interference reduction problem from a graph theoretical viewpoint. A graph coloring methods are exploited to model the interference reduction problem. However, additional constraints to graph coloring scenarios that account for various networking conditions result in additional complexity to standard graph coloring. This paper reviews a variety of algorithmic solutions for specific network topologies.

KEYWORDS

Interference Reduction, Wireless Networks, Graph Coloring, Vertex & Edge Coloring

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/3111jgraph04.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2011.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] K.C. Almeroth, E. M. Belding, M. M. Buddhikot, K. N. Ramachandran, (2006) "InterferenceAware Channel Assignment in Multi-Radio Wireless Mesh Networks,"
- [2] W. Arbaugh, S. Banerjee, A. Mishra, (2005) "Weighted Coloring Based Channel Assignment for WLANs," ACM SIGMOBILE Mobile Computing and Communications Review, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 19-31.
- [3] M. Barbeau, P. Bose, P. Carmi, M. Couture. E. Kranakis, (2006) "Location Oblivious Distributed Unit Disk Graph Coloring" School of Computer Science Carleton University pp. 1-20.
- [4] R. Battiti, A. A. Bertossi, M. A. Bonuccelli, (1999) "Assigning Codes in Wireless Networks: Bounds and Scaling Properties," Wireless Networks, pp. 195-209.
- [5] A. A. Bertossi, C. M. Pinotti, R. B. Tan, (2000) "Efficient use of radio spectrum in wireless networks with channel separation between close stations," Workshop on Discrete Algorithms and Methods for MOBILE Computing and Communications and Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Discrete Algorithms and Methods for Mobile Computing and Communications, pp. 18-27.
- [6] T. Chiueh, K. Gopalan, A. Raniwala, (2004) "Centralized Channel Assignment and Routing Algorithms for Multi-Channel Wireless Mesh Networks," ACM SIGMOBILE Mobile Computing and Communications Review, vol. 8 no. 2, pp. 50-65.
- [7] D. J. Goodman, N. B. Mandayam, C. U. Saraydar, (2002) "Efficient Power Control Via Pricing in Wireless Data Networks," IEEE Transactions on Communications, vol. 50, issue 2, pp. 291- 303.
- [8] S. Khanna, K. Kumaran, (1998) "On Wireless Spectrum Estimation and Generalized Graph Coloring," INFOCOM '98. Seventeenth Annual Joint Conference of the IEEE Computer and Communications Societies. Proceedings. IEEE, vol. 3, pp. 1273-1283.
- [9] C. McDiarmid, B. Reed, (2000) "Channel Assignment and Weighted Coloring," Networks, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 114-117.
- [10] R. Ramanathan, R. Rosales-Hain, (2000) "Topology Control of Multihop Wireless Networks Using Transmit Power Adjustment," INFOCOM 2000. Nineteenth Annual Joint Conference of the IEEE Computer and Communications Societies. Proceedings. IEEE, vol. 2, pp. 404-413.
- [11] Scalable Network Technologies, Inc. QualNet Network Simulator. 2007. <http://www.scalablenetworks.com>.
- [12] Andrew Muir, J.J. Garcia-Luna-Aceves, (1998) "A channel access protocol for multihop wireless networks with multiple channels,"
- [13] P. Karn. Maca (1990) "a new channel access method for packet radio," In Proceedings of ARRL/CRRL Amateur Radio Computer Networking Conference.

Coverage and Connectivity Aware Neural Network Based Energy Efficient Routing in Wireless Sensor Networks

1Neeraj Kumar,2 Manoj Kumar,3R.B. Patel

1,2School of computer Science and Engineering, SMVD University, Katra (J&K), India

3Department of Computer Science and Engineering, MITS University, Sikar, Rajassthan

Abstract

There are many challenges when designing and deploying wireless sensor networks (WSNs). One of the key challenges is how to make full use of the limited energy to prolong the lifetime of the network, because energy is a valuable resource in WSNs. The status of energy consumption should be continuously monitored after network deployment. In this paper, we propose coverage and connectivity aware neural network based energy efficient routing in WSN with the objective of maximizing the network lifetime. In the proposed scheme, the problem is formulated as linear programming (LP) with coverage and connectivity aware constraints. Cluster head selection is proposed using adaptive learning in neural networks followed by coverage and connectivity aware routing with data transmission. The proposed scheme is compared with existing schemes with respect to the parameters such as number of alive nodes, packet delivery fraction, and node residual energy. The simulation results show that the proposed scheme can be used in wide area of applications in WSNs.

Keywords

Sensor networks, Energy Efficiency, Routing metric, Linear Programming, Neural Networks, coverage and connectivity.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/0310jgraph5.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2010.html>

REFERENCES

- [1]. N. Al-Karaki, A.E. Kamal, (2004) "Routing techniques in wireless sensor networks: a survey", IEEE Wireless Communications, 11:6, 6–28.
- [2]. P. Bates, (1995) "Debugging heterogeneous distributed systems using event based models of behavior", ACM Transactions on Computer Systems, 13: 1.

- [3]. C. Frei, (2000) Abstraction techniques for resource allocation in communication networks, Ph.D. dissertation, Swiss Federal Inst. Technology (EPFL), Lausanne, Switzerland..
- [4]. Cerpa, N. Busek, D. Estrin, (2003) "Scale: A tool for simple connectivity assessment in lossy environments", Tech. Rep. 21, Center for Embedded Networked Sensing, University of California, Los Angeles, CA, USA.
- [5]. M. Yarvis, W. Conner, L. Krishnamurthy, J. Chhabra, B. Elliott, (2002) "A. Mainwaring, Real-world experiences with an interactive ad hoc sensor network", in: Proceedings of the 31st IEEE International Conference on Parallel Processing Workshops, ICPPW, IEEE Computer Society, Vancouver, BC, Canada.
- [6]. J. Zhao, R. Govindan., (2003) "Understanding packet delivery performance in dense wireless sensor networks", in: Proceedings of the 1st ACM International Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems, SENSYS, ACM Press, Los Angeles, CA, USA.
- [7]. D. Niculescu, (2005) "Communication paradigms for sensor networks", IEEE Communications Magazine, 43: 3, 116–122.
- [8]. J.H. Chang, L. Tassiulas, (2000) "Energy conserving routing in wireless adhoc networks", in: Proceedings of IEEE INFOCOM.
- [9]. R.C. Shah, J.M. Rabaey, (2002) "Energy aware routing for low energy ad hoc sensor networks", in: IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), March, 2002, Orlando, IEEE Communications Society.
- [10]. S. Lindsey, C. Raghavendra, K.M. Sivalingam, (2002) "Data gathering algorithms in sensor networks using energy metrics", IEEE Transactions on Parallel & Distributed Systems, 13:9, 924–935.
- [11]. W. Ye, J. Heidemann, D. Estrin, (2002) "An energy-efficient MAC protocol for wireless sensor networks", Proceedings of the 21st Annual Joint Conference of the IEEE Computer and Communications Societies (INFOCOM'02), 3:1567–1576.
- [12]. T.V. Dam, K. Langendoen, (2003) "An adaptive energy-efficient MAC protocol for wireless sensor networks", in: Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems (SenSys'03), Los Angeles, CA, November 2003, 171–180.
- [13]. G. Lu, B. Krishnamachari, C. Raghavendra, (2004) "An adaptive energy efficient and low-latency MAC for data gathering in sensor networks", in: Proceedings of the 4th International IEEE Workshop on Algorithms for Wireless, Mobile, Ad Hoc and Sensor Networks (WMAN'04).
- [14]. W.R. Heinzelman, A. Chandrakasan, H. Balakrishnan, (2000) "Energy efficient communication protocol for wireless micro sensor networks", in: Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS).
- [15]. O. Younis, S. Fahmy, (2004) "Heed: A hybrid, energy-efficient, distributed clustering approach for ad hoc sensor networks", IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, 3: 4, 366–379.

- [16]. C. Li, M. Ye, G. Chen, J. Wu, (2005) “An energy-efficient unequal clustering mechanism for wireless sensor networks”, in: Proceedings of the 2 nd IEEE International Conference on Mobile Ad-hoc and Sensor Systems (MASS’05).
- [17]. M. Demirbas, A. Arora, V. Mittal, (2004) “Floc: A fast local clustering service for wireless sensor networks”, in: Orkshop on Dependability Issues in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks and Sensor Networks (DIWANS/DSN)..
- [18]. S. Bandyopadhyay, E.J. Coyle, (2003) “An energy-efficient hierarchical clustering algorithm for wireless sensor networks”, in: IEEE INFOCOM, 3, 1713–1723.
- [19]. T. Moscibroda, R. Wattenhofer, (2005) “Maximizing the lifetime of dominating sets”, in proc. of 19th International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium.
- [20]. S.V. Pemmaraju, I.A. Pirwani, (2006) “Energy conservation in wireless sensor networks via dominating partitions”, in: MOBIHOC 06.
- [21]. H.O. Tan, I. Korpeoglu, Power efficient data gathering and aggregation in wireless sensor networks, Issue on Sensor Network Technology, SIGMOD Record.
- [22]. Sangho Yi , Junyoung Heo , Yookun Cho , Jiman Hong, (2007) “PEACH: Powerefficient and adaptive clustering hierarchy protocol for wireless sensor networks”, Computer Communications, 30:2842–2852.
- [23]. Qun Zhao, Mohan Gurusamy, (2008) “Connected K-target coverage problem in wireless sensor networks with different observation scenarios”, Computer Networks, 52: 2205–2220..
- [24]. Yan Jin, Ju-Yeon Jo, Ling Wang, Yoohwan Kim, Xiaozong Yang, (2008) “ECCRA: An energy-efficient coverage and connectivity preserving routing algorithm under border effects in wireless sensor networks”, Computer Communications, 31: 2398–2407.
- [25]. S.Soro, W.B. Heinzelman, (2008) “Cluster Head Election Techniques for Coverage Preservation in Wireless Sensor Networks”, Ad Hoc Networks.
- [26]. Deepti S. Nandiraju a, Nagesh S. Nandiraju b, Dharma P. Agrawal, (2009) “Adaptive state-based multi-radio multi-channel multi-path routing in Wireless Mesh Networks”, Pervasive and Mobile Computing, 5: 93-109.
- [27]. J. H. Chang and L. Tassiulas, (2004) “Maximum lifetime routing in wireless sensor networks”, In IEEE/ACM Trans. Networking 12:609–619.
- [28]. T. Zhao and Q. Zhao, (2007) “Coverage-based information retrieval for lifetime maximization in sensor networks”, in: Proceedings of the Conference on Information Sciences and Systems (CISS), Baltimore, 220–225.
- [29]. K. Fall and K. Varadhan (editors), (2000) “NS notes and documentation”, The VINT project, LBL, <http://www.isi.edu/nsnam/ns/>.

[30]. H.H. Zhang, J.C. Hou, (2005) "Maintaining sensing coverage and connectivity in large sensor networks", International Journal of Wireless Ad Hoc and Sensor Networks, 1 (1-2), 89–124

Citation count 16

Secure Key Exchange and Encryption Mechanism for Group Communication in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks

S. Sumathy¹ and B.Upendra Kumar²

**¹School of Computing Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India
ssumathy@vit.ac.in**

²School of Computing Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

ABSTRACT

Secured communication in ad hoc wireless networks is primarily important, because the communication signals are openly available as they propagate through air and are more susceptible to attacks ranging from passive eavesdropping to active interfering. The lack of any central coordination and shared wireless medium makes them more vulnerable to attacks than wired networks. Nodes act both as hosts and routers and are interconnected by Multi-hop communication path for forwarding and receiving packets to/from other nodes. The objective of this paper is to propose a key exchange and encryption mechanism that aims to use the MAC address as an additional parameter as the message specific key to encrypt]and forward data among the nodes. The nodes are organized in spanning tree fashion, as they avoid forming cycles and exchange of key occurs only with authenticated neighbors in ad hoc networks, where nodes join or leave the network dynamically.

Keywords

Ad hoc networks, Spanning tree, Neighborhood key, Message specific key

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/papers/0310jgraph2.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/graphhoc/current2010.html>

REFERENCES

[1] Jorg Liebeherr, Guangyu Dong, "An overlay approach to data security in ad-hoc networks" Science Direct, Ad Hoc Networks, pp. 1055-1072, July 2006.

- [2] Matthew J. Moyer, Josyula R. Rao, Pankaj Rohatgi, and Thomas.J, "A Survey of Security Issues in Multicast Communications", IEEE Network, November 1999.
- [3] David Manz, Jim Alves-Foss and Shanyu Zheng, "Network Simulation of Group Key Management Protocols", Journal of Information Assurance and Security, pp. 67-79, January 2008.
- [4] Lidong Zhou and Zygmunt J. Haas, "Securing Ad Hoc Networks", IEEE Network, November 1999.
- [5] Vesa Kärpijoki, "Security in Ad Hoc Networks", Seminar on Network Security, 2000.
- [6] X.B. Zhang, S.S. Lam, H. Liu, "Efficient group rekeying using application-layer multicast", in Proceedings of the 25th IEEE International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems, (ICDCS 2005), June 2005.
- [7] C. Gui, P. Mohapatra, "Efficient overlay multicast for mobile ad hoc networks", in Proceedings of IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), March 2003.
- [8] Y.C. Hu, A. Perrig, "A survey of secure wireless ad hoc routing", IEEE Security and Privacy 2 (3) (2004).
- [9] Kevin Fall, Kannan Varadhan, "The ns manual", The VINT project, December 2008.
- [10] Brent Welch, "Practical Programming in Tcl and Tk", Prentice Hall, May 1994.